

Fostering Innovation, Integration and Inclusion Through Interdisciplinary Practices in Management

A Review – Mobile App for Retail Industry

Miss. Avanti A. Patil.¹ Dr. Kulkarni R. V.²

¹Department of M.Phil, Computer Application, ² Head of the Department, Computer Application, ^{1,2}Chhatrapati Shahu Institute of Business Education and Research, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India

Organised By:

Management Department, Chhatrapati Shahu Institute of Business Education and Research, Kolhapur, Maharashtra

An Autonomous Institute Under UGC & Shivaji University College with Potential for Excellence (CPE) - III Phase.

ABSTRACT

In several years the use of E-Commerce and its popularity are excessively growing. Retail industry is also playing the major role in E-Commerce. Retail is the process of selling consumer goods or services to customers through multiple channels of distribution to earn profit. The growing number of internet users provides a great opportunity for online retail market. Innovative mobile technologies provide new features through mobile application by allowing consumers to make purchases by Smartphone. In this paper author had reviewed the role of Mobile Applications for Retail Industry.

How to cite this paper: Miss. Avanti A. Patil. | Dr. Kulkarni R. V. "A Review – Mobile App for Retail Industry" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Special Issue | Fostering Innovation, Integration and Inclusion Through Interdisciplinary Practices in Management, March 2019, pp.24-26, URL: <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd23054.pdf>

IJTSRD23054

KEYWORDS: Retailing, Mobile Applications, Online Shopping

INTRODUCTION Retailing

Retailing is the business where an organization directly sells its products and services to an end consumer. Retail involves the sale of goods from one single point directly to the consumer in small quantities. Retail is a type of sales where the selling is done from a fixed location, such as a departmental store for direct use by the purchaser. The word Retailer has been derived from the French word "Retail" which means sell in small quantities from different wholesalers and sell them to the ultimate consumer he is the last link in the chain of distribution from the producer to the consumer. Generally the supply chain contain four major parts first is manufacturer who produce the good, second one is Wholesale suppliers or Distributer who buy from manufacturers, third one is retailers who buy products from Wholesale suppliers and last one is customers retailers who sell out the products to the customers.

Retail Shop

Retail Shop or Departmental Store is large retail accumulation which handles a vast variety of products. Retail is the store which sells products or services in smaller

quantities to the general public. It is a business that operates as a retail hoard will typically buy products or goods directly from wholesale suppliers or manufacturers at a large volume and will then mark them up in a price for distribution of sale to end customers. Departmental Store is organized into separate Departments for purpose of buying, promoting, services and control.

Retail Store mainly contains grocery, clothing, food, bakery products, dairy products furniture, home appliances, toys, cosmetics, home care products, gardening, sporting goods, stationary products, hardware. Other products like books, jewelry, electronics, baby products, photographic equipments, products for pets. In retail store many products are available since from necessary items up-to luxury items. Retailing mainly involves customer expectations and needs, retailer always try to show the merchandise in effective manner so that customer find that easily and that product should be attractive to buy and retail shops also try to developing good merchandise assortments and performs

services of bulk breaking i.e. repackaging of products in small units according to customers convenience

Generally retailers have to maintain the main pillars like quality of product, loyalty, trust of consumers, good customer services, and customer satisfaction, retailer should take care about these things, because these things are important to maintain a good relationship with customers if a customer is satisfied with your services, quality of products then they will definitely first prefer that retail shop for shopping, and will also do mouth publicity that will help to collect more customers.

Application:

An Application or Mobile Application is a software program designed to run on a specific hardware. A mobile application used for Smartphone and Tablets which are designed with phantom for the demands. Mobile Applications helps users by connecting them to internet services and makes it easier to use the internet.

Mobile Phones are important in today’s world. If you observe around you, you will see that every second person is busy with mobile by doing something on mobile like messaging, searching chatting, online shopping, watching videos, playing games and so many other things, it happens because of the craze of mobiles or it might be because of busy schedule the usage of mobile are increasing day by day every work should be possible through mobile and its applications. Mobile Applications are more convenient and comfortable than a websites because of the portability feature of mobile. A mobile application plays a vital role to provide convenience to users. And this intent is beneficial to Retailers to enhance their business through mobile applications there is great chance to grab more customers by providing them a mobile application.

Reasons why people prefers Mobile Application

Preferences App vs. Mobile Site

Mobile Applications are simple to use because of the convenience and faster performance customers choose mobile applications for shopping. Mobile Application provides interactive user interface. It may works offline

There are some benefits of mobile apps:

1. Customer can order their product at any time, there will be no time restrictions and they can order from anywhere no matter physically where the customer is available.

2. Retailer can do more advertisement using application which replaces the printed pamphlets advertisement.
3. Retailer can provide cash on Delivery options or other options like online payment using Credit cards it will make the payment mode easy.
4. Retailer can give user a better experience or practicable way of shopping.
5. The app will help retailers to keep in touch with clients
6. Retailer can give some extra facilities like points on purchasing or discounts to user
7. App will help to retailer to display a proper and detail information about each and every product, displaying pictures of products that will also give clearance about that product.
8. Application provides so many features to customers like Add to cart, Wish list, push notifications, reminders on sale periods.
9. Retailer will be aware about customer satisfaction by receiving the feedback or complaints regarding a particular product.
10. Mobile App will help to maintain the status of retail shop.
11. Mobile Apps save time and decreases traffic.

Retail Industry is the fastest growing sector in Indian Economy. Traditional markets are developing in new formats such as Departmental Stores, Shopping Malls, Super Markets, Hyper Markets and Bazaars like Special Shops for Retailing. All of these large departmental stores have been developed in Metro Cities or Big Cities in India and the development is also proceeding in small cities. These Shopping Malls or Departmental Stores gives world class experience to customers.

Some of the departmental stores or retailers in metro cities developed their own Mobile applications for customer to enhance business and decrease traffic. It has some restrictions such as their service is available only for particular area or just for a metro city they provide limited area wise services. As comparing with metro cities very rare development is done in small cities most of the departmental store does not use mobile applications for marketing. In small cities some departmental stores or retail shops has huge amount customers who visited weekly, monthly to the same retail store because of quality of product and trust. Regular Customers or customers who visited newly they have to visit store for purchasing their orders. There is no development of mobile applications from retailers for customers to decrease traffic. Awareness of developing mobile application is not that much done in small cities as compared to metro cities. Retailers should develop Mobile Application which can be beneficial to retailer to enhance business and also beneficial for customers to shop online.

Review of Literature:

In this review the use of mobile application for retail shop and consumer is described:

In this research article author explains the usefulness of mobile application are increased in several years mobile applications usability is based on applications effectiveness, efficiency and customer satisfaction so at the time of developing an application developer have to consider these things.[1]

In this research article Roger Strom, Martin Vendel, John Bred can explains Mobile shopping is easy comparing with desktop shopping because it providing features like scanning, GPS facilities, and camera and the of mobiles is independent on time and place.[2]

In this research paper Venkata N Inukollu, Divya D Keshamoni, Taeghyun kang and Manikanta Inukollu explains mobile application developers should develop standard quality of applications according to standard development life cycle using new technologies involving with new features. [3]

In this research article Maja kiba-Janik explains Mobile shopping is helpful to customers for quick searching of products through mobile. Retail stores use mobile applications for providing facilities to customers like new promotions, events, information about new products. [4]

In this research article author explains nowadays customers prefers Smartphone for shopping. Retailers should develop mobile applications as per customer demands, convenience and customer satisfaction. Retailers have grasp that customers are very picky about the retailers app they use. [5]

In this research paper Mr. Elenora pantano explains the advanced mobile technologies give better shopping experience. Consumers are shifting from e-channels to mobile channels and to think upon the development of new technologies. [6]

In this research article Mr. Rahul Kumar explains the growth of online shopping is tremendously increased in India customers come to know the benefits of online shopping. If the Retailer understands the need of customers or buying tendency of customers then it will help to develop standard application [7]

In this research article Ville Turkia explains Mobile applications are important part of retail business. If the mobile application considers customer point of view for shopping, good marketing strategies while developing then it will beneficial to retailer. [8]

In this research paper Ms. Ayushi Y. Vadawala and Ms. Maitri S. Vadawala explains in recent years the craze of e-commerce is increased because of its convenient way of exchanging goods and global services. [9]

In this research article Zulekha Fatima, Charu Bisaria, Ajay Prakash explains Retailer should develop horizon for different types of products, services, providing detail information about product, technological improvement, visual merchandising that will help to grab more customers. [10]

In this research paper Shilpa Jain explains increasing number of internet users in India gives a great opportunity to online retail market to develop their business. Some features provided by mobile application like online payment, internet banking, E-wallet and cash-on-delivery these modes of payment make transaction easy. [11]

Conclusion:

Nowadays everything is possible using mobile. Customers are preferring mobiles for shopping to save their time there is great opportunity for retailers, they should start developing their own mobile applications considering with customer need and expectations to provide them a good shopping experience. There are some mobile application developed by retail stores in metro cities but their service is limited for that certain area as comparing with metro cities very rare development is done for small cities. Retailers in small cities has to focus on mobile marketing by develop mobile applications in small cities to provide better services to customers.

References:

- [1] Rachel Harrison Email author Derek Flood David Duce, Open Access Research (2013)
- [2] Mobile Marketing: A Literature review on its value for consumers and retailers Roger Strom, Martin Vendel, John Bredican (2013)
- [3] Factors influencing quality of mobile Apps : Role of mobile app development life cycle. Venkata N Inukollu, Divya D Keshamoni, Taeghyun kang and Manikanta Inukollu (2014)
- [4] The use of Mobile phones by customer in retail store. Maja kiba-Janik (2014)
- [5] Forrester Research (2015)
- [6] The effect of Mobile Retailing on consumers purchasing experiences. Mr. Elenora pantano (2016)
- [7] The Future of Online shopping in India. Rahul Kumar (2016)
- [8] Managing Customer value: A study of mobile Applications. Ville Turkia (2016)
- [9] E- Commerce: Merits and Demerits: Ms. Ayushi Y. Vadawala and Ms. Maitri S. Vadawala (2017)
- [10] Retailing an emerging trend in India. Zulekha Fatima, Charu Bisaria, Ajay Prakash (2017)
- [11] Perspective of online retailing in India: Shipa Jain (2018)

Copyright © 2019 by author(s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

